

PLANETARY Health Cluster

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MOSAIC

SPRINGS

TULIP
planetary health

Common Cluster Data Management Plan

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1. Executive summary

This document provides an overview of the data-related synergy-enhancing activities within the Planetary Health Cluster. The Cluster was officially launched during the online meeting on 26th of March 2024 with the participation of the coordinators of the five projects funded under the Horizon Europe topic HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-01 “Planetary health: understanding the links between environmental degradation and health impacts”. The five projects that form the Planetary Health Cluster are GoGreen Next, MOSAIC, PLANET4HEALTH, SPRINGS, and TULIP.

This Cluster-level data management plan (DMP) is a living document and will be revised at M24 and M36.

The following sections give an overview of the first draft of a Cluster-level DMP across the projects in the Planetary Health Cluster. The purpose of this document is to provide a shared DMP describing synergetic elements that go beyond the individual project DMPs.

2. Introduction

The projects in the Planetary Health Cluster aim to improve identification, monitoring, and quantification of the direct and indirect impacts of environmental changes and degradation on Planetary Health. All projects within the Cluster were funded under the Horizon call HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-01, which addresses the health impacts of environmental changes and degradations.

The Planetary Health Cluster was set up by the European Commission to allow the five projects to:

- Harmonise approaches
- Promote synergies and networking
- Avoid overlaps
- Strengthen the Science4Policy link
- Streamline information flows
- Improve communication and dissemination
- Increase their impact.

The Cluster’s objective is to provide clarity on the costs and benefits of action and inaction of mitigation and adaptation to environmental changes. The main objectives of the Planetary Health Cluster are:

1. Promote and disseminate environment and health research from a Planetary Health perspective.
2. Raise awareness of the health impacts of environmental changes and the costs and benefits of mitigation and adaptation interventions.
3. Maximise the communication and dissemination of results through the projects’ networks.
4. Contribute to evidence-based decision-making and stronger EU and global policies.

5. Build capacity around environment and health research.

The purpose of this Cluster-level data management plan (DMP) is to describe synergetic elements that go beyond the individual project's DMP and yield added value, in line with the European Commission's rationale for establishing the Cluster. This Cluster-level DMP serves to facilitate: 1) identifying areas of collaboration across projects; 2) reducing duplication of effort across projects; and 3) ensuring data availability and access beyond the duration of the cluster.

The objectives of the Cluster-level DMP are:

1. To identify areas of added value of collaboration in the collection, mapping, sharing, and reuse of data (including metadata), and the development of tools and protocols.
2. To develop plans for implementing these collaborations.
3. To ensure robust quality assurance across the cluster's data management.

3. Data typologies

This section outlines the types of data the Cluster will collect, process, and generate. The developed Data Mapping Tool contains data across all Cluster projects, detailing format, size, origin, reuse potential, utility, and level of openness. The tool offers an overview of the Cluster's evolving data landscape, highlighting both the diversity of datasets and opportunities for collaboration.

During the initial phase of Cluster activities realization, the data mapping tool will serve as a source of internal information about the kinds and types of data each project will use and collect. Working Group 2 (WG2) will coordinate this process, ensuring consistency and timely updates in collaboration with the project leads. As the Cluster develops, the tool will be refined to reflect emerging needs. It will allow to develop the future plans for data sharing within the Cluster, and procedures to make this possible. This will be part of the second iteration of this document. The tool will serve both as a working resource and a reference point. It may be shared, distributed, or published at the end of the Cluster activities realization, as an example of what kinds of datasets the complex work on Planetary Health issues entails.

The data is classified between types of data, project, sector/domain, target end users, spatial-temporal coverage, etc. The latest version of the Data Mapping Tool is available [here](#).

Building on this internal resource, a catalogue of data-metadata (with related DOIs when applicable) collected during the projects will be built, published, and maintained on the cluster web page. This catalogue will include data that are already described in, and possibly accessible through existing data repositories and services (like the Copernicus data store, NASA data repositories etc.) insofar as they have an interest in a Planetary health perspective. However, it is worth specifying that the cluster does not aim to redistribute third-party data. For personal and confidential data (health data, etc.) a contact person and institution that will be responsible for data sharing after the end of the project will be mentioned.

3.1 Opportunities for data sharing

This section provides an overview of data types (including meta-data) that could be shared across projects and the timeline for these potential data-sharing opportunities.

The initial proposal for providing added value in data collection, management, and sharing is listed below and will be updated in subsequent versions of the DMP:

1. Sharing metadata.
2. Sharing best practices regarding implementing FAIR data principles, data security, and ethical considerations.
3. Sharing links and/or unique resource identifiers (e.g. DOI) to data and code published in open repositories (e.g. Zenodo, GBIF, Github, Gitlab), within the Cluster where applicable.

3.2 Promoting FAIR principles

All five projects across the Cluster have committed to ensure that the data produced/collected satisfies the criteria of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR), and ensure access to the data as open as possible, as closed as needed, beyond Cluster duration. At this early stage of the Planetary Health Cluster, it is not yet established what data will be shared within the Cluster, making detailed descriptions of data handling according to the FAIR principles premature. Therefore, this section gives a brief overview of how these criteria will be implemented across the Cluster. Later versions of this document will provide more detail on how FAIR principles for data sharing across the Planetary Health Cluster will be implemented. The projects will work on a data transfer agreement template for the Cluster to facilitate data sharing.

All five projects will share knowledge, experiences, and results concerning metadata standards and controlled vocabularies they developed or selected, in order to develop a metadata model adapted to the 'planetary health' approach.

3.2.1 Making data findable

Data will be annotated with metadata, and databases will be assigned a unique identifier in the form of digital object identifiers (DOIs).

At the Cluster level, we plan to create a spreadsheet stored on the Cluster Google Drive with an overview of databases generated through the Cluster projects, with links to the metadata stored in the repository used by each project. This repository will be accessible by the Cluster working groups and coordinators.

3.2.2 Making data accessible

Three types of data will be generated in the projects:

- a) data that will be made openly available and usable by third parties;
- b) data that will be restricted due to privacy concerns but usable by third parties under a proper agreement; and
- c) human sensitive data will be fully anonymized and/or de-identified before sharing, which will be available on request to a dedicated contact person/institution.

The projects are committed to ensuring that data are 'as open as possible, as closed as needed'. Where possible, and where appropriate, access requests have been addressed, access to data will be ensured. Where data is shared and made available externally, this will be disseminated as appropriately outlined in the dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan (i.e., via the broader cluster mailing list).

3.2.3 Making data interoperable

Making data interoperable allows for use between the partners and across research projects and supports their subsequent further re-use by third parties. Creating data sets in well-understood, non-proprietary, and common formats supports interoperability. For example, publishing tabular data as a .csv file will be readable by more software than Excel files. It will be more easily extractable and reusable than if published as a table in a .pdf document. Currently, the output data format is still under consideration and will be determined once the methods and methodologies of data analytics are agreed upon.

The Planetary Health Cluster projects will provide data in a machine-readable format that can contribute to a new interoperable ontology. How to maximally implement interoperability is currently under discussion. Therefore, details on this aspect of data management will be given in follow-up iterations. Currently, only the internal data standards have been considered within individual projects, while standards to ensure project output datasets are interoperable are under discussion.

3.2.4 Increase data re-use

To facilitate the broadest dissemination and impact of scientific peer-reviewed publications, including on related data/metadata generated in the Cluster, results will be published open access under open licences, with three steps approach: (i) The projects in the Cluster will, whenever possible, share preprints with the research community. As journal peer review can be a slow process, preprints will accelerate the communication of research results and ensure early impact; (ii) publications will be placed in open access journals or make use of fully open access options in journals offering this option; and (iii) the five projects will archive final publications in trusted repositories that allow immediate open access.

As much as possible, scientific and data papers will be associated with the datasets uploaded in repositories or listed in data catalogues, to:

- describe the method of production (hypotheses, models);
- qualify the data (absolute and/or relative evaluation, biases identification, and quantification when possible);
- give exploitation examples.

At least, data description (production, qualification, use) will be part of the metadata.

When access is granted, the application of the most open licence (CC BY 4.0 – only credit must be given to the creator, or CC0 – public domain), depending on data specificities, will be favoured to facilitate data access and reuse.

3.2.5 Allocation of resources

Resources needed for the implementation of the Cluster DMP include:

1. Sharepoint for sharing documents - this has already been established by the Cluster.
2. Platform for holding webinars or online workshops (e.g., Zoom) - we will use platforms used by individual institutions or projects. No further resources are anticipated at this stage.
3. Human resources for carrying out the work - human resources will be covered by consortium members of the individual projects.

4. List of participants in WG2

Name	Project affiliation
Marina Treskova	TULIP
Uliana Kachnova	TULIP
Jacob Grosfeld	TULIP
Chona Mae Daga	TULIP
Luise Nottmeyer	TULIP
Emmanuel Roux	MOSAIC
Lukasz Dumiszewski	MOSAIC
Filipe Dias Lewandowski	MOSAIC
Stephane Debard	MOSAIC
Victor Mose	MOSAIC
Vanessa Harris	SPRINGS
Cyril Caminade	SPRINGS
Rik Oldenkamp	SPRINGS

Debraj Roy	SPRINGS
Suzana Blesic	PLANET4HEALTH
Gaia Bertarelli	PLANET4HEALTH
Stefano Campostrini	PLANET4HEALTH
Daniel San Martín	PLANET4HEALTH
Paul Quinn	PLANET4HEALTH
Karen Cruyt	PLANET4HEALTH
Sergio Natal	PLANET4HEALTH
Mario Balzan	GoGreen Next
Kai Gensitz	GoGreen Next
Niamh Cahill	GoGreen Next
Franck Lascaux	GoGreen Next
Tadhg MacIntyre	GoGreen Next
Claudio Nigg	GoGreen Next

5. Ethics

The following principles will be applied when processing personal data: lawfulness, fairness, and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimization (necessary and proportionate for the research objective); accuracy; storage limitation; and integrity and confidentiality.

Each project will carry out ethics approvals from appropriate local and/or national institutional review board and collect human data in line with the WMA Declaration of Helsinki for medical research involving human participants where relevant. Data-sharing agreements will be used where appropriate. All data will be stored and processed in line with FAIR principles, the GDPR, Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing, and where necessary individual country data protection legislation.

At the Cluster level, we will share best practices on ethical issues related to project data. We will do this on an “ad hoc” basis within Working Group 2 as ethical issues arise during the projects. We may, for example, organize an online webinar to identify and adjust key issues and best practices.

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